

Guia Básico para Uso do Biblioshiny

1. Objetivos do material

- Instalação dos softwares R
- Importação do arquivo para o Biblioshiny
- Apresentação das principais análises realizadas pelo software, incluindo as estatísticas descritivas de dados obtidos junto aos artigos para fins de análise bibliométrica

Carga horária: 2 horas

Instrutores: Michele e Eli

Data: 28/03/2025 (Sexta-feira)

Horário: 14h00 – 16h00

2. Referências de artigos sobre revisão sistemática

Exemplos de artigos de análise bibliométrica e revisão sistemática que usam o Biblioshiny

Artigo 1 – Huang, S. S. (2025). A comprehensive science mapping of tourism and hospitality research: Tribes, territories and networks. *Journal of Hospitality, Leisure, Sport & Tourism Education*, 36, 100523, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhlste.2024.100523>.

Artigo 2 – Abu, N., da Silva, F. P., & Vieira, P. R. (2024). Government support for SMEs in the Fintech Era: Enhancing access to finance, survival, and performance. *Digital Business*, 5(1), 100099. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.digbus.2024.100099>

Artigo 3 – dos Reis Cardillo, M. A., & Basso, L. F. C. (2025). Revisiting knowledge on ESG/CSR and financial performance: A bibliometric and systematic review of moderating variables. *Journal of Innovation & Knowledge*, 10(1), 100648. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jik.2024.100648>

Artigo 4 - Secinaro, S., Lanzalonga, F., Oppioli, M., & de Nuccio, E. (2025). The effects of disruptive technologies on accountability in fintech industry: Using bibliometric analysis to develop a research agenda. *Research in International Business and Finance*, 76, 102816. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ribaf.2025.102816>

Referência de artigo sobre o pacote Bibliometrix

Artigo 5 - Aria, M. & Cuccurullo, C. (2017) bibliometrix: An R-tool for comprehensive science mapping analysis, *Journal of Informetrics*, 11(4), 959-975. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joi.2017.08.007>

Artigo 6 - Aria, M., Cuccurullo, C., & Aria, M. M. (2024). Package ‘bibliometrix’.

Artigo 7 - Ab Rashid, M. F. (2023). How to conduct a bibliometric analysis using R packages: A comprehensive guidelines. *Journal of Tourism, Hospitality and Culinary Arts*, 15(1), 24-39. <https://ir.uitm.edu.my/id/eprint/87654>

3. Instalação do software R

Baixe e instale a versão mais recente do R, clicando em <https://cran.r-project.org>

Clicar em Download R for Windows

Download and Install R

Precompiled binary distributions of the base system and contributed packages, **Windows and Mac** users most likely want one of these versions of R:

- [Download R for Linux \(Debian, Fedora/Redhat, Ubuntu\)](#)
- [Download R for macOS](#)
- [Download R for Windows](#)

R is part of many Linux distributions, you should check with your Linux package management system in addition to the link above.

Clicar em Install R for the first time

R for Windows

Subdirectories:

base	Binaries for base distribution. This is what you want to install R for the first time .
contrib	Binaries of contributed CRAN packages (for R >= 4.0.x).
old contrib	Binaries of contributed CRAN packages for outdated versions of R (for R < 4.0.x).
Rtools	Tools to build R and R packages. This is what you want to build your own packages on Windows, or to build R itself.

Please do not submit binaries to CRAN. Package developers might want to contact Uwe Ligges directly in case of questions / suggestions related to Windows binaries.

You may also want to read the [R FAQ](#) and [R for Windows FAQ](#).

Note: CRAN does some checks on these binaries for viruses, but cannot give guarantees. Use the normal precautions with downloaded executables.

Clicar em Download R-4.4.2 for Windows (83 megabytes, 64 bit)

R-4.4.2 for Windows

[Download R-4.4.2 for Windows \(83 megabytes, 64 bit\)](#)

[README on the Windows binary distribution](#)
[New features in this version](#)

This build requires UCRT, which is part of Windows since Windows 10 and Windows Server 2016. On older systems, UCRT has to be installed manually from [here](#).

If you want to double-check that the package you have downloaded matches the package distributed by CRAN, you can compare the [md5sum](#) of the .exe to the [fingerprint](#) on the master server.

4. Exclusão de artigos duplicados - Scopus e Web of Science – no R

Passo 1 - Instalação dos pacotes básicos do R e Bibliometrix

```
install.packages("openxlsx")
```

Obs: Se o sistema perguntar: Would you like to use a personal library instead? Clique em YES e depois escolha a opção Brazil (SP 1) [https] e Clicar em OK

```
install.packages("bibliometrix")
```

```
library("bibliometrix")
```


Passo 2 - Consolidação das bases de dados no R

```
file <- c("scopus.bib")
M <- convert2df(file, dbsource = "scopus", format = "bibtex")
```

```
file <- c("savedrecs.bib")
W <- convert2df(file, dbsource = 'wos', format = "bibtex")
```

Passo 3 - Exclusão dos artigos duplicados no R e download do arquivo final - em .xlsx

```
Database <- mergeDbSources(M, W, remove.duplicated = TRUE)
```

```
View(Database)
```

```
dim(Database)
```

```
library(openxlsx)
```

```
write.xlsx(Database, file = "Database.xlsx")
```


Obs: No seu diretório **C:\Users\SEU NOME\Documentos**, devem aparecer três arquivos, sendo:

Nome	Status	Data de modificação	Tipo	Tamanho
Database.xlsx	✓	24/02/2025 19:24	Planilha do Micros...	496 KB
savedrecs.bib	✓	24/02/2025 17:58	Arquivo BIB	1.375 KB
scopus.bib	✓	24/02/2025 17:47	Arquivo BIB	396 KB

Passo 4 – Acesso ao Biblioshiny no ambiente web a partir do R

Obs: O arquivo Database.xlsx será salvo em C:/Usuários/SEU NOME/Documentos

biblioshiny()

Obs: Deve abrir a seguinte página no seu ambiente web:

```
R Console
Generating affiliation field tag AU_UN from C1: Done!
> file <- c("savedata.xlsx")
> W <- convert2df(file, dbsource = "woa", format = "bibtext")
Converting your woa collection into a bibliographic dataframe
Done!
Generating affiliation field tag AU_UN from C1: Done!
> Database<-mergeDbSources(M,W, remove.duplicated = TRUE)
106 duplicated documents have been removed
> View(Database)
> dim(Database)
[1] 205 54
> library(openxlsx)
> write.xlsx(Database, file = "Database.xlsx")
> biblioshiny()
```


5. Informações iniciais sobre o Biblioshiny

Como usar o Biblioshiny

Please follow the biblioshiny tutorial at:

www.bibliometrix.org/biblioshiny

<http://www.bibliometrix.org/biblioshiny/assets/player/KeynoteDHTMLPlayer.html#0>

https://www.bibliometrix.org/vignettes/Introduction_to_bibliometrix.html

Video: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9YwVhFEovCA>

O Biblioshiny é um aplicativo que fornece uma interface da web para bibliometrix.

Ele apoia os estudiosos no uso fácil dos principais recursos do bibliometrix:

- o Importação de dados e conversão para coleta de quadro de dados
- o Coleta de dados usando Dimensions, PubMed e coleta de APIs Scopus
- o Filtragem de dados
- o Analytics e Plots para três métricas de nível diferentes:

- Fontes
- Autores
- Documentos

o Análise de três estruturas de conhecimento (estruturas K):

- Estrutura Conceitual
- Estrutura Intelectual
- Estrutura Social

Alguns conceitos importantes

Global Citations (TC) means the Total Citations that an article, included in your collection, has received from documents indexed on a bibliographic database (WoS, Scopus, etc.). So, TC counts citations received by a selected article "all over the world".

In **Most Cited References**, Bibliometrix counts the local citations, in other words, the citations that a reference (a document included in, at least, one of the bibliographies of the articles in your collection) has received from documents included in your collection.

The reference lists include all documents from bibliographies as then many of the references could not be part of your collection! When a reference is also part of your collection, it is called "Cited document".

So, **Local citations** are citations received by a reference article "internally to your collection".

- A cited document is a document cited by other document of the same collection
- It belongs both in the Document Set and in the Reference Set

Data frame columns are named using the standard Clarivate Analytics WoS Field Tag codify:

Field Tag	Description
AU	Authors
TI	Document Title
SO	Publication Name (or Source)
J1	ISO Source Abbreviation
DT	Document Type
DE	Authors' Keywords
ID	Keywords associated by SCOPUS or ISI database
AB	Abstract
C1	Author Address
RP	Reprint Address
CR	Cited References

TC	Times Cited
PY	Year
SC	Subject Category
UT	Unique Article Identifier
DB	Bibliographic Database

An object of class “bibliometrix” is a list containing the following components:

List element	Description
Articles	the total number of manuscripts
Authors	the authors’ frequency distribution
AuthorsFrac	the authors’ frequency distribution (fractionalized)
FirstAuthors	corresponding author of each manuscript
nAUpperPaper	the number of authors per manuscript
Appearances	the number of author appearances
nAuthors	the number of authors
AuMultiAuthoredArt	the number of authors of multi-authored articles
MostCitedPapers	the list of manuscripts sorted by citations
Years	publication year of each manuscript
FirstAffiliation	the affiliation of the corresponding author
Affiliations	the frequency distribution of affiliations (of all co-authors for each paper)
Aff_frac	the fractionalized frequency distribution of affiliations (of all co-authors for each paper)
CO	the affiliation country of the corresponding author
Countries	the affiliation countries’ frequency distribution
CountryCollaboration	the intra-country (SCP) and inter-country (MCP) collaboration indices
TotalCitation	the number of times each manuscript has been cited
TCperYear	the yearly average number of times each manuscript has been cited
Sources	the frequency distribution of sources (journals, books, etc.)
DE	the frequency distribution of authors’ keywords
ID	the frequency distribution of keywords associated to the manuscript by SCOPUS and Thomson Reuters’ ISI Web of Knowledge databases

6. Importação da base de dados – arquivo Database.xlsx

Na página do Biblioshiny da internet, seguir esses comandos, clicando em:

Data / Import or Load. Em: Please, choose what to do, escolher: Load bibliometrix file(s). Em: Choose a file: Importar o arquivo.xlsx – **ex: Database** / Start

Obs: Esse arquivo Database foi obtido a partir dos critérios de pesquisa apresentados na Aula 2 sobre ANÁLISE BIBLIOMÉTRICA/REVISÃO SISTEMÁTICA que ocorreu no dia 21/03/2025. O tema de pesquisa refere-se à ESG and “valuation” e os anos de análise são de 2015 a 2024.

Completeness of metadata -- 205 docs merged from 2 DBs

Original size docs -- Deleted duplicated docs

Metadata	Description	Missing Counts	Missing %	Status
C1	Affiliation	0	0.00	Excellent
AU	Author	0	0.00	Excellent
DT	Document Type	0	0.00	Excellent
SO	Journal	0	0.00	Excellent
LA	Language	0	0.00	Excellent
PY	Publication Year	0	0.00	Excellent
TI	Title	0	0.00	Excellent
TC	Total Citation	0	0.00	Excellent
AB	Abstract	1	0.49	Good
RP	Corresponding Author	5	2.44	Good
DI	DOI	5	2.44	Good
DE	Keywords	11	5.37	Good
ID	Keywords Plus	45	21.95	Poor
CR	Cited References	205	100.00	Completely missing
WC	Science Categories	205	100.00	Completely missing

[Advice](#)
[Report](#)
[Save](#)
[Close](#)

7. Exemplos de análises do Biblioshiny

Na barra azul à esquerda, escolher os tipos de análise desejadas pelos seguintes critérios: Overview, Sources, Authors, Documents, Clusterings, Conceptual Structure, Intellectual Structure, Social Structure. Dica: **Após escolher a análise, clicar em Run, quando indicado.**

Overview

Overview / Main information / Plot

Overview / Main information / Table

The screenshot displays a web application interface for data analysis. The main content area is titled "main information" and shows a table with two columns: "Description" and "Results". The table is currently displaying 1 entry out of 22, with a "Previous" and "Next" navigation bar at the bottom. The table content is as follows:

Description	Results
MAIN INFORMATION ABOUT DATA	
Timespan	2015:2025
Sources (Journals, Books, etc)	128
Documents	205
Annual Growth Rate %	16.23
Document Average Age	2.6
Average citations per doc	35.4
References	0
DOCUMENT CONTENTS	
Keywords Plus (ID)	448
Author's Keywords (DE)	746
AUTHORS	
Authors	562
Authors of single-authored docs	24
AUTHORS COLLABORATION	
Single-authored docs	24
Co-Authors per Doc	2.96
International co-authorships %	29.76
DOCUMENT TYPES	
article	180
article article	1
article, early access	24

Showing 1 to 22 of 22 entries

Overview / Annual Scientific Production / Plot

Overview / Average Citations Per Year/ Plot

Overview / Three-Field Plot

Em que:
 DE - Authors' Keywords
 AU – Authors
 AU_CO – Authors countries

Parameters

Field	Number of items
Middle Field Authors	20
Left Field Keywords	20
Right Field Countries	20

Porém, sempre é possível alterar os parâmetros da análise...

Análise dos periódicos - Sources

Sources / Most Relevant Sources

Sources / **Bradford's Law**

Sources / Source Local Impact

Obs: Local citations are citations received by a reference article "internally to your collection".

Sources / Sources' Production over Time

Análise dos autores - Authors

Authors / Most Relevant Authors

Authors / Authors' Production over Time

Authors / Lotka's Law

Authors / Authors' Local Impact

Authors/ Affiliations / Most Relevant Affiliations

Authors/ Affiliations / Affiliations' Production over Time

Authors / Countries / Corresponding Author's Country

Obs: Country Collaboration: the intra-country (SCP) and inter-country (MCP) collaboration indices

Authors / Countries / Country Scientific Production

Authors / Countries / Countries' Production over Time

Authors / Countries / Most Cited Countries

Análise dos artigos - documents

Documents / Most Global Cited Documents

Obs: Artigos da amostra citados por outros artigos fora da amostra

Documents / Cited References / Most Local Cited References

Obs: Referências mencionadas nos artigos da amostra citadas pelos artigos da amostra

Documents / Reference Spectroscopy

Obs: Espectroscopia das referências – Apresenta a evolução e concentração cronológica das referências mencionas nos artigos da amostra

Marx, W., Bornmann, L., Barth, A., & Leydesdorff, L. (2014). **Detecting the historical roots of research fields by reference publication year spectroscopy (RPYS)**. *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 65(4), 751-764. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.23089>

Documents / Words / Word Tree Map / Keywords Plus

Documents / Words / Word Tree Map / Author's keywords

Documents / Words / Words' Frequency over Time

Documents / Words / Trend Topics

8. Outras opções de análises do Biblioshiny

Data / Load data / Import or Load: Use a sample collection / Start

Clustering

Clustering /Clustering by coupling / Network

It performs a coupling network analysis and plots community detection results on a bi-dimensional map (Coupling Map).

Conceptual structure

Conceptual Structure / Network approach / Co-occurrence network

Social Structure

Social Structure / Collaboration Network

Social Structure / Countries' Collaboration World Map

